

gaseous N losses through volatilization and denitrification. We experimented with 3 levels of pyrite (0, 40%, and 60% of gypsum requirement [GR]) and N (40, 80, and 120 kg/ha) in a randomized block design with 3 replications.

The sodic soil had pH 9.2, ECe 7.2 dS/m, ESP 38, hydraulic conductivity 0.18 cm/h, and sandy loam texture. Pyrite containing 22% sulfur was mixed into the top 10-cm soil. Moisture was maintained between field capacity and saturation for 1 wk before transplanting to enhance oxidation. Jaya rice seedlings 40-d-old were planted at 4-5/hill in unpuddled soil. The crop was raised with ponded water following recommended agronomic practices. N was applied in 3 splits; half before

Effect of iron pyrites on grain yield of rice, and uptake and percent recovery of applied N at 40, 80, and 120 kg/ha. ^aFaizabad, India.

Pyrite (%) of GR	N uptake (kg/ha)			Grain yield (t/ha)			Change in soil pH (1:2:5)
	40	80	120	40	80	120	
No pyrite	4.9 (5.5)	7.2 (5.6)	8.2 (4.6)	1.22 (-)	1.61 (-)	1.85 (-)	9.2
40	7.4 (11.8)	10.4 (9.6)	14.0 (9.4)	2.10 (74.5)	2.75 (70.8)	3.00 (67.6)	8.6
60	8.8 (15.3)	13.6 (13.6)	16.2 (11.3)	2.66 (118.0)	3.56 (121.0)	3.86 (108.6)	8.3

^aN uptake in control = 2.7 kg/ha. Grain yield in control = 0.8 t/ha. Values in parentheses indicate percent recovery of applied N and percent response to N with pyrites, respectively.

transplanting, 1/4 one mo after transplanting, and 1/4 at panicle initiation.

Pyrite increased recovery of applied N

(see table). Maximum N recovery was with 60% GR and 40 kg N/ha. Grain yield also increased with pyrite application. □

Disease management

Effect of micronutrient on rice brown spot (BS) incidence

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BS caused by *Helminthosporium oryzae* can cause up to 20% yield losses in tropical rice. The disease occurs mostly after late tillering, when micronutrients are needed for the reproductive phase. We studied the influence of soil and foliar applications of micronutrients on BS incidence during 1985-86 and 1986-87, using IR20 as test variety.

The micronutrients were applied as foliar sprays, on the soil, or as both soil and foliar sprays (see table). Soil application was done before transplanting; leaves were sprayed 30 and 50 d after transplanting (DT). Natural incidence of BS was recorded on 20 leaves/plot at the dough stage and the disease index calculated by McKinney's formula.

BS incidence was lowest with soil application of 25 kg FeSO₄/ha + 0.5% foliar spray 30 and 50 DT, or with soil

BS incidence at different levels of micronutrients. ^a Madurai, India, 1985-87.

Micronutrient	Treatment		Percentage disease index	
	Application	Dosage	1985-86	1986-87
CuSO ₄	Foliar spray	0.5%	20.9 (27.20)	18.4 (25.40)
ZnSO ₄	Foliar spray	0.5%	24.0 (29.33)	18.1 (25.18)
MnSO ₄	Foliar spray	0.5%	19.6 (26.27)	19.1 (25.92)
MgSO ₄	Foliar spray	0.5%	24.1 (29.40)	22.1 (28.04)
FeSO ₄	Foliar spray	0.5%	24.9 (29.93)	18.0 (25.10)
ZnSO ₄	To soil	20 kg/ha	21.4 (27.56)	21.2 (27.42)
FeSO ₄	To soil	25 kg/ha	25.2 (30.13)	26.2 (30.79)
MnSO ₄	To soil	25 kg/ha	25.0 (30.00)	25.6 (30.40)
CuSO ₄	To soil	1 kg/ha	20.00 (26.56)	22.2 (28.11)
CaSO ₄	To soil	500 kg/ha	23.7 (29.13)	30.4 (33.46)
CuSO ₄	To soil + foliar spray	1 kg/ha + 0.5%	16.1 (23.66)	15.5 (23.19)
ZnSO ₄	To soil + foliar spray	20 kg/ha + 0.5%	32.7 (34.88)	17.9 (25.03)
MnSO ₄	To soil + foliar spray	25 kg/ha + 0.5%	20.4 (26.85)	22.6 (28.38)
FeSO ₄	To soil + foliar spray	25 kg/ha + 0.5%	16.7 (24.12)	14.9 (22.79)
Control		—	40.6 (39.58)	35.6 (36.63)
LSD (P=0.05)			(2.156)	(2.222)

^aFigures in parentheses are transformed values.

application of 1 kg CuSO₄ / ha + 0.5% foliar spray 30 and 50 DT. Foliar sprays of CuSO₄ and MnSO₄ 30 and 50 DT were also effective in minimizing BS incidence. Grain yield was not affected by any treatment. □

Status of sheath rot (ShR) in eastern Uttar Pradesh (UP), India

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We observed ShR symptoms in rice cultivar TN1 in 1966 wet season (WS) at Kalyanpur, Kanpur, UP. As TN1 spread, and later Jaya, ShR became highly noticeable throughout UP. We isolated the causal fungus in 1977, identifying it as *Sarocladium oryzae* (Sawada) Gams and Hawksworth.

From 1977 to 1987, we surveyed eastern UP, finding ShR in all 5,000 sites visited.

Reaction of scented and export quality rice varieties and cultures to ShR. Faizabad, UP, India, 1980-1981.

Varieties or culture	Disease score ^a
BPMS69, BPMS40 A, Kala Namak, KSR white	1
BPMS1, KSR49-89-10, RP967-11-14-2	2
Basmati 370, HAU11-12, PAU269-1-9-2-1, HPU8106, TR-B-63	3
ADT32	4
BPMS39, Improved Sona, Ratna, SST-2-1909, Type 3, UPR79-1, HAU5-162-3, HAU232-2, Pusa 150	5
AD14185, BK79, BPMS36, BPMS40, BPMS66, Bas 370-A-132-3-9, HAU5-298-2, KSR47-87-1, NM Badshah Pasand, PAU14-2-5-B-5-2-1, PAU29-295-3-3-4-1-1, PAU269-1-9-1-2, PAU269-2-31-1-4, Pusa 150-9-3-1, Pusa 150-9-4-1, Pusa 150-21-1-1, Pusa 167, Badshah Pasand	6
HAU5-30-2, PAU269-1-9-2-4, PAU269-1-9-3, UPR227-9-2-1, UPR227-22-1-1, UPRM 500	7
TN1	9

^a By the *Standard evaluation system for rice* (1980).

Drought, excess rain, green leafhopper, brown planthopper and stem borer infestations and tungro infections contributed to ShR incidence.

When ShR spread in epidemic proportions in 1980 and 1981 WS, we field-tested 46 scented and export quality rice varieties and cultures for resistance to the disease (see table). BPMS69, BPMS40A, Kala Namak, KSR white (all scored 1), BPMSI, KSR49-89-10, RP967-11-1-4-2 (all scored 2), Basmati 370, HAU11-12,

PAU269-1-9-2-1, HPU8106, TR-B-63 (all scored 3) were resistant.

Carbofuran granules at 1.0 kg ai/ ha at 60 d after transplanting (DT) have economically controlled the disease in cultivar Jaya. Similar results were obtained with 3 sprays of monocrotophos or edifenphos at 0.5 kg ai/ ha, at 15-d intervals, beginning 60 DT. Carbendazim, sprayed as above, controlled the disease but was not economical. □

Rice disease incidence in South Gujarat, India

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Rice in South Gujarat is attacked by a number of diseases every year, that cause considerable losses. We surveyed the occurrence and severity of rice diseases at different crop stages in three districts of South Gujarat during 1983, 1984, and 1985 wet seasons (WSs).

Two to three plots were selected at eight sites and four areas per plot were sampled. Disease intensity was rated according to the *Standard evaluation system for rice* and disease severity categorized as no infection (0), trace (1), moderate (3-5), and severe (7-9).

During 1983 WS, bacterial blight was moderate at all sites except at Nanikarod, where infection was severe in only GR11 and TN1 (check). In 1984, it was severe in GR11, TN1, and IR22 at all sites except Bardoli. In 1985, it was severe at four and moderate at three sites.

Blast was severe in Sathi 34-36 at Navsari in 1983. It was not observed in 1984 but in 1985, it was found in Sathi 34-36 and Mashuri at two sites: Navsari and Vyara.

False smut was found in a moderate form at five sites in 1983; in a moderate form at two sites, and in trace form at one site in 1984; and in moderate to severe form at two sites in 1985.

Kernel smut was observed only at one site, in IR22 in 1983.

Phyllosticta leaf blight in moderate form was observed only in 1983 at Chikhali and Navrasi. Stem rot was found at Navrasi in a severe form only in Entry No. 6869 in 1983 and in Mashuri in 1984.

Udbatta was in moderate form in Halki-Kolam only at Pipalpada in 1983 and 1984. □

A simple method of estimating rice blast (Bl) severity

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Our objective was to develop a simple disease assessment method that can be used by extension workers and farmers. Leaf Bl was assessed in 22 farmers' fields in central Thailand during 1987 dry season. Using a systematic diagonal sampling of 0.16 ha, 10 samples of tillers per field were taken. The top four leaves of each tiller were assessed separately for Bl severity. Average severity for leaves 1 to 4, as well as average severity of all leaves, was calculated for each field. Incidence (infected leaves among the top 4 leaves) was calculated from 400 leaves/field. Average severity (% leaf area damaged) of the top four leaves